

The Influence of the make a Match Learning Model on the German Writing Ability of Class XI Science Students at SMA YP HKBP PematangSiantar

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this research is to see the effect of the Make A Match learning model on the German writing skills of Class XI Science Students at SMA YP HKBP Pematang Siantar. This research uses quantitative methods with an experimental research approach and a One Group Pretest-Posttest research design. The population in this study was Class XI students, totaling 34 people. The sample used was 19 people, namely class XI Science students at SMA YP HKBP Pematang Siantar. The conclusion of the research is that the Make A Match learning model influences the German writing ability of class XI IPA students at YP HKBP Pematang Siantar High School. This is proven by an increase in the average student score on the pretest of 52.63 below the KKM and on the posttest of 85.00 above the KKM. The results of the normality test show that the significance value of the pretest data is 0.053 and the posttest significance value is 0.067, so it can be concluded that the sign significance (Sig.) is > 0.05 , so the research data is normally distributed. This is proven by the results of statistical hypothesis analysis tests using paired sample tests which produce a sign significance of $0.001 < 0.05$, which means Sig. (2-sided p) < 0.05 , it is concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted.

INTRODUCTION

The use of foreign languages in this era of globalization has a very important role. Using and mastering foreign languages allows humans to communicate and interact with other humans in all countries in the world. Apart from mastering foreign languages, humans can follow developments in science and technology, catch up and find out what is happening in the world easily.

In learning German there are four language skills, namely: Hörverstehen (listening skills), Sprechfertigkeit (speaking skills), Leseverstehen (reading skills), Schreibfertigkeit (writing skills). Among the four German language skills, writing skills are skills that are difficult for someone to master.

Because learning is only dominated by teachers, learning seems monotonous and students are less interested in participating in learning.

This makes it difficult for students to understand how to understand German with these four skills, especially writing skills. Writing is considered the most complex skill, because in writing there are many things that need to be considered. Things that need to be considered in writing are content, coherence, vocabulary and structure. Learning German in the 2013 curriculum studies various different texts in each of the predetermined KDs that have been established in the 2013 curriculum. These texts are divided into the competencies stated in the syllabus. One of the basic competencies (KD) that must be achieved in learning German according to the 2013 curriculum for YP HKBP PematangSiantar High School students is writing skills. In writing skills, students are expected to be able to write words, phrases and sentences with correct letters, spelling and punctuation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Nature of German Language Learning

Language is the ability possessed by humans to communicate with other humans using signs, for example words and movements. Personally, language is a tool for expressing inner ideas to other people. Finnochiaro in Hardjono (1988: 8) interprets language as an arbitrary vocal system that allows people in certain communities or other people who have learned the system to communicate or interact.

A person is said to have mastered a language if that person understands what other people say and can apply it to communicate. The opinion of Purwanto and Alim (1997: 20) is that the purpose of language is to form understanding. The point is that by learning a language, especially a foreign language, the speaker must be able to understand what other people are saying.

In German, what must be learned is German language skills. There are four skills in German, namely:

1. listening skills (Hörverstehen),
2. reading skills (Leseverstehen),
3. speaking skills (Sprechfertigkeit),
4. writing skills (Schreibfertigkeit).

Learning a foreign language, especially German, is a language learning process that students carry out intentionally, both in formal and informal

forums, and the language studied by language students is a language other than the language of the country itself. Learning German for students means studying various aspects of the language which together form a unity. The aim of learning German is so that students can use the language to communicate with people outside the language used in their country, whether studied orally or in writing.

The Nature of German Writing Skills

Writing is essentially composing which gives shape to everything to the mind, and through the mind, everything that is felt, takes the form of a series of words, especially written words that are arranged as well as possible so that the reader can understand and benefit from them easily. Writers usually convey the contents of their thoughts by involving the attention of their readers.

Table 1. Achievement of Writing Skills

Basic competencies	Indicator Reached
4.1 Write words, phrases and sentences with correct letters, spelling and punctuation .	4.1.1. Complete the words with vowels in the short text about Essen und Trinken. 4.1.2. Write German words from short texts. 4.1.3. Write simple German sentences with correct spelling and punctuation so that it becomes a complete text.
4.2 Disclosing information in an appropriate manner written in simple sentences according to context, which reflects ability to use words, phrases with letters, spelling, punctuation and structure correctly .	4.2.1. Arrange words into sentences by reflecting skills in using words, phrases with letters, spelling, punctuation and correct structure.

(Source: 2013 Curriculum Syllabus Data for SMA YP HKBP)

The Nature of The Cooperative Learning Model

The model is a conceptual framework used as a guide in carrying out activities. A learning model can be interpreted as a conceptual framework that describes systematic procedures for organizing learning experiences to achieve learning goals. Achieving a learning objective requires model options that suit the characteristics of the learning object.

Applying the correct learning model will have a good effect on the student's learning process which ultimately shows the achievement of learning indicators. For this learning model, the teacher directs students to explain the problem solving plan into activity stages, the teacher gives examples of the use of skills and strategies needed so that the tasks can be completed well.

Make a match Type Cooperative Learning Model

The make a match learning model comes from cooperative learning , where this model uses a system of grouping students heterogeneously working

together to achieve learning goals. This grouping system allows students to be active and makes learning more effective and efficient.

There are various types of cooperative learning models, one of which is make a match . The make a match learning model is one type of cooperative learning model. The make a match model was first developed in 1994 by Lorna Curran. In the make a match learning model, students are invited to learn while playing. According to Huda (2013: 251) states that the make a match type cooperative learning model is a type of concept learning model, inviting students to look for answers to something.

Figure 2.1. Framework of Thought

METHODOLOGY

The type of design used by researchers is One Group Pretest-Posttest Design Sugiyono (2013: 74-75). In one class the experiment was carried out twice, namely before and after treatment. Pretest (O_1) is before carrying out treatment, and Posttest (O_2) is after carrying out treatment. The results of the Pretest and Posttest treatment can be seen how the Make A Match learning model influences the writing ability of class XI students at SMA YP HKBP PematangSiantar. This design can be described as follows:

Table 3.1. Research design

Pretest	Treatment	Posttest
O_1	X	O_2

Information:

O_1 = Pretest (Initial test score): writing ability before using the Make A Match learning model

X = Treatment: applying the M make A Match learning model in learning
 O₂ = Posttest (Final test score): writing ability after using the Make A Match learning model

RESEARCH RESULT

The number of students in the experimental class was 19 people. Students work on Pretest and Posttest questions. Research in the experimental class, namely class XI Science, YP HKBP PematangSiantar High School, presented the results data, namely:

Table 2. Pretest Descriptive Statistical Data Analysis

Statistics		
Pretest		
N	Valid	19
	Missing	0
Mean		52.63
Median		55.00
Mode		55
Std. Deviation		9,032
Variance		81,579
Minimum		40
Maximum		70
Sum		1000

The table above can be explained that the average (Mean) Pretest value is 52.63. with a total of 19 students. With the lowest value (Minimum) being 40 and the highest value (Maximum) being 70, the middle value (Median) totaling 55.00, the variance value is 81,579, the standard deviation (Std. Deviation) is 9,032, the mode value is 55. and the total number of numbers in the data (Sum) is 1000. So it can be concluded from the results of the average value. On average, there was no increase in the scores of class XI IPA students regarding writing ability. So there must be a Make A Match learning model for the German writing skills of class XI IPA students at SMA YP HKBP PematangSiantar so that students' grades increase.

Table 3. Posttest Data Statistik Data Analysis

Statistics		
Posttest		
N	Valid	19
	Missing	0
Mean		85.00
Median		85.00
Mode		85
Std. Deviation		5,528
Variance		30,556
Minimum		75

Maximum	95
Sum	1615

The table above explains that the average (Mean) Posttest score is 85.00 , and the number of students is 19 people, with the lowest (Minimum) score being 7.5 and the highest (Maximum) score being 95 , the middle score (Median) amounting to 85.00, the variance value is 30,556, the standard deviation (Std. Deviation) is 5,528, the mode value is 85. and the total number of numbers in the data (Sum) is 1615. So it can be concluded from the results of the average value. In the posttest average, there was an increase in the grades of class XI IPA students regarding writing ability. So there is an influence of the Make A Match learning model on the German writing ability of class XI IPA students at SMA YP HKBP Pematang Siantar.

Data Normality Test Results

If the significance value (Sig.) is greater than 0.05 then the research data is normally distributed, conversely, if the significance value (Sig.) is smaller than 0.05 then the research data is not normally distributed. Test the normality of this data using IBM SPSS 29 for Windows.

Table 5.Data Normality Test Table

Tests of Normality			
	Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistics	df	Sig.
Pretest	902	19	053
Posttest	908	19	067

The table above explains that the significance value (Sig.) for the pretest is .053, for the statistical value (Statistics) it is 0.902, and the degree of freedom (df) is 19. Then the significance value (Sig.) for the posttest is 0.067, for the statistical value (Statistics) it is 0.098, and the degree of freedom (df) is 19, so it can be concluded that the significance value (Sig.) between the pretest and posttest is greater than 0.05, so the research data is normally distributed.

Hypothesis testing

1. H_0 : There is no influence of the Make A Match learning model on the German writing skills of class XI IPA students at SMA YP HKBP Pematang Siantar.
2. H_1 : There is an influence of the Make A Match learning model on the German writing skills of class XI IPA students at SMA YP HKBP Pematang Siantar.

Table 6. T Test Paired Samples Test

Paired Samples Test										
		Paired Differences					t	df	Significance	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				One-Sided p	Two-Sided p
					Lower	Upper				
Pair 1	Pretest - Posttest	-32.368	8.395	1.926	-36.414	-28.322	-16.807	18	<,001	<,001

The table above explains that the average value (Mean) on the pretest and posttest is -32.368, the standard deviation (Std. Deviation) value of the pretest and posttest is 8.39, the average standard error value (Std. Error Mean) of the pretest and posttest totaling 1,926, 95% range of confidence figures for the average pretest and posttest scores (95% Confidence Interval for Mean) the lowest pretest and posttest score (Lower Bound) is -36,414 , and the highest pretest and posttest score (Upper Bound) is -36.414. -28,322 . The pretest and posttest t (test) values are -16.807 with degrees of freedom (df) totaling 18. The pretest and posttest significance values are 0.001, so it can be concluded that it is smaller than 0.05, meaning there is a significant influence. In the sense that if the Sig value. (2-sided p) < 0.05, then Ho is rejected and H₁ is accepted. In conclusion, there is an influence of the Make A Match learning model on the German writing ability of YP HKBP Pematang Siantar High School students.

DISCUSSION

The aim of this research was to determine the effect of the Make A Match learning model on the German writing skills of Class XI students at SMA YP HKBP PematangSiantar. The type of research used is an experimental approach with One Group Pretest-Posttest Design. The research population was class XI with a sample of one experimental class, namely class

Research stage, Pretest is carried out before providing treatment according to the research design. Then after that, treatment is given by applying the Make A Match learning model, and ends with a Posttest. The time allocation is 2 x 45 minutes, in six lesson hours or the equivalent of three meetings.

When the research stage is complete, the next step is to carry out data analysis on the Pretest and Posttest results. Value results The pretest average

was 52.63 with the highest score being 70 and the lowest score being 40 . Meanwhile, the results show that the average value The posttest is 85.00 with the highest score being 95 and the lowest score being 65. These results can be concluded that the average posttest score is higher than the average pretest score.

Then the average results of the pretest and posttest were known, then a data normality test was carried out using Shapiro Wilk in order to see the normality of the pretest and posttest score data in the Make A Match learning model regarding writing ability. The calculation results of the pretest significance value were 0.053 and the posttest significance value was 0.067 , so it was concluded that the significance value (Sig.) was greater than 0.05, so the research data was normally distributed, in the sense that the pretest and posttest value data for Class X I students Science at SMA YP HKBP PematangSiantar is in the normal category.

To determine the statistical hypothesis, the Paired Samples T-Test was used. The results of the Paired Samples T-Test obtained a significance value of $0.001 < 0.05$ in the sense of the Sig value. (2-sided p) < 0.05 , then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. Thus, the Make A Match learning model influences the writing skills of class XI Science students at YP HKBP Pematang Siantar High School.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

After the data analysis was carried out carefully and thoroughly, the researcher was able to come up with a conclusion, namely that there was a significant influence of the Make A Match learning model on the writing ability of class XI Science students at SMA YP HKBP Pematang Siantar, so it was concluded that:

1. The results of the average value of students' writing skills before being given treatment (Pretest) was 52.63 and the average value after being given treatment (Posttest) was 85.00 , it can be concluded that the Make A Match learning model has an effect on the writing skills of Class XI Science Students YP HKBP Pematang Siantar High School.
2. There is evidence using the data normality test using Shapiro Wilk with a pretest significance value of 0.053 and a posttest significance value of 0.067 , so it can be concluded that the significance value (Sig.) is greater than 0.05, so the research data is normally distributed. Then from the results of the Hypothesis test that has been carried out, the Sig value is obtained. (2-sided p) < 0.05 , namely $0.001 < 0.05$, so the hypothesis H_1 in this study is accepted and successful.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions above, there are several suggestions as follows;

1. Suggestions for Teachers
Make A Match learning model so that students are more interested in taking part in other lessons, especially German language lessons.

2. Advice for Students

Using the right learning model in learning is one of the factors that can help achieve learning goals. Therefore, learning media should be used in the process of teaching and learning activities, so that students play an active role in participating in learning activities, and make it easier for students to carry out the tasks given.

3. Suggestions for Researchers

Researchers are expected to be able to develop and strengthen the results of this research by conducting further research related to the Make A Match model in writing skills.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

Each study has limitations; thus, you can describe it here and briefly provide suggestions for further research.

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